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Case Report

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Acneiform eruption due to erlotinib treatment: a case report

ABSTRACT

Erlotinib is a quinazoline derivative that selectively and reversibly inhibits the tyrosine kinase activity of EGFR and is used in the treatment of advanced non-small cell lung cancer. Common mucocutaneous side effects reported with erlotinib treatment are xeroderma, pruritus and paronychia, with acneiform eruption being the most common. Erlotinib-associated acneiform eruption usually occurs within the first 1-3 weeks of drug use, typically as asymptomatic or pruritic erythematous papules and/or pustules on the face, chest, abdomen and thighs. Here, we report a 56-year-old woman with non-small cell lung cancer who developed erlotinib-associated acneiform eruption.

Keywords: Acne, Acneiform eruption, Erlotinib

Introduction

Erlotinib is an oral chemotherapy drug belonging to the class of epidermal growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitors and is widely used in the treatment of advanced non-small cell lung cancer and pancreatic cancer. EGFR is a receptor that plays an important role in cell proliferation, differentiation, and survival. However, these receptors are also highly expressed in the epidermis, particularly in keratinocytes. Therefore, the use of EGFR inhibitors may lead to various adverse effects on the skin.

Among the most commonly reported dermatological side effects in patients treated with erlotinib are acneiform eruptions. These rashes typically appear within the first few weeks of starting the medication and are often localized on the face, chest, and back. Although they resemble acne in clinical appearance, their pathogenesis is different and they may not always respond to conventional acne treatments (1).

In this case presentation, the clinical course of a 56 years old patient who developed a pronounced acneiform eruption while undergoing erlotinib treatment and the treatment with a gel containing 3% erythromycin ,5% benzoyl peroxide and doxycycline capsules will be discussed.

The timely recognition and appropriate management of such side effects are important for maintaining patients' quality of life and ensuring treatment continuity. Timely recognition and appropriate management of such side effects are important for maintaining patients' quality of life and ensuring treatment adherence.

CASE REPORT

A 56 years old woman presented to our outpatient clinic with a sudden onset skin rash on the face. It was learned from her history that she was diagnosed with non-small cell lung cancer one month ago and

had been receiving erlotinib treatment for 9 days. The rash started on the cheeks and spread to the nose and chin for the last 3 days. Dermatologic examination revealed pustules on a monomorphic erythematous background especially on the nose, chin, upper lip and cheeks and yellow crusts on the chin.(Figure 1) The lesions were not accompanied by comedones and were asymptomatic. The patient was diagnosed as acneiform eruption due to erlotinib. The patient was started on gel containing 3% erythromycin ,5% benzoyl peroxide, doxycycline capsule and fusidic acid was given to the impetiginized areas with yellow crusts on the chin. The dose and frequency of erlotinib treatment could not be changed. The patient's lesions regressed almost completely in 1 month follow-up.

DISCUSSIONS

The epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) is a transmembrane tyrosine kinase receptor expressed in many epithelial tumors (1). EGFR plays a role in pathways related to tumor cell proliferation, apoptosis, angiogenesis, and metastasis. High levels of EGFR expression have been detected in tumor cells of the head, neck, lung, breast, ovary, prostate, and colon (2). EGFR plays a role in the normal differentiation of epidermal keratinocytes, the stimulation of epidermal growth, protection against ultraviolet-induced damage, inhibition of inflammation, and acceleration of wound healing. EGFR is expressed in normal epidermal and follicular keratinocytes, the basal layer of the epidermis, the outer root sheath of the hair follicle, sebaceous epithelium, eccrine epithelium, dendritic antigen-presenting cells, and various connective tissue cells (3). Various skin toxicities, such as papulopustular lesions, xerosis, pruritus, nail changes, hair changes, telangiectasia, hyperpigmentation, and mucositis, have been reported with EGFR inhibition. Although the pathogenesis of skin toxicities caused by EGFR inhibitors is not fully understood, inflammation and changes in keratinocyte proliferation, differentiation,

and migration are thought to cause skin symptoms (4-5).

Acneiform rash associated with erlotinib usually begins within the first 1-3 weeks of drug use. It typically presents as asymptomatic or pruritic erythematous papules or pustules on the face, chest, abdomen, and thighs (6). Unlike acne vulgaris, pustules are sterile, there are no accompanying comedones, and they may be monomorphic and itchy (6-7). Unlike classic acneiform drug rash associated with systemic corticosteroid use, which is included in the differential diagnosis, it is more acute and inflammatory. Unlike acute generalized exanthematous pustulosis, involvement of skin folds is not prominent, pustules do not tend to coalesce, and they do not cause fever. The skin side effects of EGFR inhibitors are transient and decrease in severity as treatment continues. The rash resolves completely after discontinuation of treatment and rarely limits dose or treatment (8-9). There is a view that the therapeutic effect of the drug is higher in patients where this reaction is prominent and may be considered a survival marker (6-7).

In clinical trials, acneiform rash caused by EGFR inhibitors has been classified according to the National Cancer Institute's recommendations.

Grade 1: Erythema, macules, follicular localized papules/pustules, asymptomatic

Grade 2: Erythema, macules, follicular localized papules/pustules, localized desquamation, affecting less than 50% of the body, itchy or symptomatic

Grade 3: Generalized erythema, papules, pustules, vesicles, desquamation, affecting more than 50% of the body, itchy or symptomatic

Grade 4: Exfoliative or ulcerative erythroderma

Grade 5: Death

Most acne-like rashes associated with EGFR inhibitors are Grade 1 or 2 and do not cause

significant discomfort. Grade 3 and 4 rashes are seen in only 5-38% of patients (7).

The treatment of erlotinib-induced acneiform rash remains a controversial topic, and treatment approaches are generally recommended based on the severity of the rash. Treatment options include topical corticosteroids, retinoids, metronidazole, benzoyl peroxide, or systemic tetracyclines, isotretinoin, and systemic steroids for severe rashes (8-10).

In mild cases, treatment with EGFR inhibitors may not be necessary as the rash sometimes resolves spontaneously despite continued treatment. However, treatment for mild Grade 1 reactions includes traditional topical acne medications such as benzoyl peroxide, metronidazole, erythromycin, and clindamycin. In Grade 2 reactions, oral tetracyclines may be added to topical treatment (7). Oral isotretinoin has been effective even when EGFR therapy is continued (7-11).

However, since oral isotretinoin has a side effect profile that overlaps with EGFR inhibitors in terms of paronychia and xerosis, caution should be exercised in its use, and oral isotretinoin should not be used in combination with oral tetracycline therapy due to an increased risk of pseudotumor cerebri. Additionally, since acneiform rash is dose-dependent, adjusting the dosage or dosing schedule of EGFR inhibitor therapy may help manage the rash. Management of grade 3 reactions may require delaying treatment with EGFR inhibitors, oral isotretinoin, and oral tetracyclines to reduce acute inflammation. In patients with very rare Grade 4 reactions, EGFR inhibitors should be discontinued, and the patient should be managed by burn care specialists. Additionally, infected rashes respond effectively to short-term treatment with oral tetracyclines, cephalosporins, and amoxicillin/clavulanic acid (7). In the case presented by Nakahara et al., follicular pustular eruptions were observed on the face, chest, and extremities of a 47 years old patient on the 10th day of erlotinib

treatment. This patient was successfully managed with a combination therapy including oral tetracycline and topical clindamycin-benzoyl peroxide gel, and discontinuation of the drug was not necessary (12). In the case presented by Metin et al., a 67 years old patient who started erlotinib therapy developed acneiform eruptions on the face following initiation of the drug. In this case, treatment with a combination of topical clindamycin and benzoyl peroxide was administered, and treatment was continued after significant improvement in skin lesions was achieved (13).

Figure 1. Pustules on a monomorphic erythematous base on the nose, chin, upper lip, and cheeks; yellow crusts on the chin. Lesions were not accompanied by comedones

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Conclusion

In conclusion, erlotinib-induced acneiform eruption is a drug reaction with a mostly benign prognosis with features such as spontaneous regression or regression with conventional acne treatment and resolution of lesions despite continued erlotinib treatment. Here, we present a case of erlotinib-induced acneiform eruption in our clinic to emphasize the increasing use of erlotinib treatment in the etiology of acneiform eruptions and its clinical features in the light of current literature.

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